

DEGA – Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik e.V.

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Memorandum

Guidelines for implementing and documenting audio productions for scientific applications in acoustics

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1 Preface

When releasing audio recordings for artistic or cultural purposes normally it is not necessary to publish a comprehensive documentation of the recording conditions along with them.

This contrasts with the more extensive documentation required when artistically designed audio recordings containing music and speech for scientific purposes are published. Typical applications could include the use of audio materials for stimuli in auditory experiments, as source signals for stimulating electro- or virtual acoustics, or possibly as demonstration material for proofs of concept in research and development.

The fact that even recordings made in a scientific context were frequently not documented properly or only for an immediately envisaged application and one-off use resulted in many productions proving to be unsuitable for later use. Without adequate documentation it is furthermore impossible to add new recordings to existing productions under the same recording conditions.

Examples include:

- Recordings of musical instruments without documenting the absolute sound level and microphone positions, making them practically useless for synthesizing an acoustic scene in virtual acoustics,
- Music or speech recordings for applications in music information retrieval (MIR) for which the influence of diverse microphones and varying room proportions on the analysis results (audio features, classification) cannot be evaluated without documentation of the recording conditions,
- Recordings whose usefulness can only be ensured with a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio.

The above-described scientific use cases present documentation and reproducibility challenges that in particular relate to the recording process, the prevailing recording conditions, the recording systems used and postprocessing steps. Last but not least, clarifying the legal aspects covering later use and enjoyment of artistic audio contents and documenting them is called for. Free use, open access and explicit retrievability are desirable for scientific use.

The present memorandum by the technical committees for virtual acoustics, musical acoustics, and audibility acoustics it is hoped will contribute to better (re)usability of audio productions for scientific applications. It contains guidelines for documenting the production process, shows various options for handling right to use in the research context and makes recommendations concerning electronic publication to ensure sustained access and referencability.

2 The recording room and recording conditions

The room plays a decisive role in what will be heard on a sound recording. Outside the hall radius, which in the typical recording studio only measures ca. 1.3 meters, the energy of the sound reflections

Technical Committees

Virtual Acoustics / Musical Acoustics / Auditory Acoustics

overwhelms the direct sound from the source. The room influences the recorded signal through comb filter effects resulting from reflections from close-by walls and floors [1], the spatial effect of early reflections for instance on the apparent source width (ASW) [2], diffuse echo effects and background noises emanated by the room itself (ventilation noises, electrical devices) or against which the room is insufficiently soundproofed.

Documentation of the recording conditions to aid reproducibility must contain information about the room and its acoustic characteristics, the spatial configuration of sound sources and recording systems, and the background noise in the acoustic field.

2.1 Room geometry

For every recording, the documentation must specify:

- The detailed dimensions of the room (length/width/height, volume).
- A sketch of the room (layout, if possible a 3D model, e.g., as a Sketchup (.skp) or Blender (.obj)-file), showing the positions of the sound sources and recording systems (more on this below).
- Information on the type of materials used in the major surface areas (floor, ceiling).

2.2 Microphone positions

The documentation above all must comprise a geometrical sketch of the recording situation, to include especially

- The position and orientation of the microphones ,
- The distances to the sound source
- Distances from walls, floor, and ceiling
- A photo documentation of the recording session

If a 3D model of the recording room has been made, the positions of the sound sources and the microphones can be sketched in.

2.3 Room acoustics

Provide the following information:

- Room acoustics parameters, at minimum a frequency-dependent reverberation time in octave bands with details on measurement method and -equipment.
- The acoustic noise floor level where the recording microphones are located for at least a 10 second averaging period measured with a calibrated sound level meter in dB(A) (with detail on the meter used).

If known, directivity factors of each source and microphone should preferably given in octave bands.

To be enclosed with the electronic publication is the recording of a room impulse response with detail of the transmitter and receiver position in the room, information about the excitation source (measurement speaker), excitation signal and the measurement microphone (type/name/model numbers, membrane size) .

2.4 Recording systems

Provide the following:

- The recording microphones used, identified by type, name, and described in a data sheet detailing directionality, frequency response, equivalent inherent noise, transfer factor in mV/Pa.
- The electronic transmission technique used (preamp, A/D converter, audio interface)
- The preamplification used (allowing for possible attenuators)
- Optionally, if feasible: the effective preamplification factor measured by a phantom feed oscillator with a defined voltage

The electronic publication must be accompanied by:

- A recording of the sound source lasting about 10 seconds made in parallel with each microphone used in the production paired with a calibrated measurement microphone immediately next to it. The recording must be capable of being used to normalize the subsequent production to an absolute acoustic pressure in dB(A) (with details on the measuring equipment).
- A recording of the entire acoustically and electroacoustically generated noise level by recording the background noise (without sound source) lasting at least 10 seconds, with all

recording microphones at the position used for recording, stating the gain, audio effects, etc. settings used for the recording.

- Documentation of the acoustic crosstalk between the microphones used with distributed ensembles by recording short individual sequences for each instrument with all microphones in their respective positions.

3 Audio contents

Specify

- The recorded audio contents. For speech, enclose a copy of the spoken text, for music, a copy of the played score. Should this be precluded for copyright reasons or because of a disproportionately large volume of performed or spoken material, it suffices to provide a link to the (publicly accessible) source that will allow subsequent users to access the text.
- Instructions or stage directions for the playing or speaking mode during the recording.
- Names of the recorded speakers, musicians, and recorded ensembles.
- The sound sources used, e.g., the musical instruments, including type, maker, concert pitch, special features of the instrument such as string material, historical construction method, and the like.
- The duration of the individual recordings.
- The audio format, with details on the sampling rate, codec, and data format used. The recording, processing, and archiving is to be done in a data format without perceptible compression (.flac, .wav).
- The peak levels of the individual recordings in dBFS.

The above informations can be detailed in a leader for all recordings in a series or individually for each recording.

4 Right of use

The aim should be to make recorded and, if appropriate, processed audio signals freely available for use by the public, with due regard for copyright laws which differ from country to country. In Germany, copyrights cannot be relinquished or transferred. A tried and true way for signaling a release to the public is to link it to the “null” “Creative Commons” licensing logo, illustrated below:

Figure: Logo "CC Null"

An explanation of the symbol can be found under [3], to the effect that

“persons who link a work with this grant have freed its content globally – also known as ‘public domain’ – which means they give up all copyright and related protection insofar as permitted by law...you can copy the work, change it, distribute and perform it, even for commercial purposes without having to ask for further permission.”

Internationally, a language regime has to be found that addresses the different ways of handling copyrights in different countries. This mandatory international description has been formulated under [4]

In advance of the present Memorandum, DEGA commissioned the drafting of a license agreement tailored to the needs of the scientific community (see Appendix I) that is designed to deal with the right to use in the clearest possible way. This model agreement includes the following passage:

“The Artist transfers to the Licensee the exclusive right to copy, process, distribute or otherwise use each audio recording. The Artist also grants the Licensee, insofar as the Licensee is not already considered as the creator of the respective performances, the exclusive right unlimited as to time, place, and content to use each of the audio recordings in any way whatsoever”.

“Licensee” can mean The German Acoustical Society.

To make this an ironclad contract afterwards, it is important that an appropriate creative fee be paid for producing the musical or speech recordings. This effectively makes it impossible to illegally exploit artistic performances.

When disseminating audio data, e.g., on a website, always post or include the applicable legal licensing aspects.

5 Dissemination

To ensure that audio productions can be easily retrieved, readily referenced, and permanently accessed requires storing them in a research data repository that guarantees highly secure, long term archival of different data formats (audio, images, text, etc.)

By furnishing a persistent identifier (PID) – most often this means a digital object identifier (DOI) – the unique identification, referencing, and electronic access to the data as well as linking these to scientific search engines through metadata is made possible, thus assuring the retrievability of the data.

Many universities manage their own institutional repositories. A suitable institution- and discipline-spanning repository currently is the Zenodo service financed by the European Commission [5]. A data repository for acoustics under the auspices of the OPERA project is in the process of being set up; it offers discipline-specific metadata and access options, such as pre-fader playback of audiodata [6].

6 References

- [1] Brunner, S., Maempel, H.-J., Weinzierl, S. (2007). „On the audibility of comb filter distortions”, in: *122nd AES Convention*, Vienna, Austria, Paper 7047.
- [2] Barron, M. Marshall, A.H. (1981). “Spatial impression due to early lateral reflections in concert halls: The derivation of a physical measure”, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 77(2), 211-232.
- [3] <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.de>
- [4] <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/legalcode>
- [5] Zenodo Repository, URL: <https://zenodo.org>
- [6] Weinzierl, S., Kern, H. (2017). „An Open Repository for Research Data in Acoustics (OPERA)”, in: *Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 2017* (Kiel), 226-228.
- [7] Leckschat, D., Epe, C., Spors S., Weinzierl S. und Zotter, F. (2017). „DEGA-Projekt ‚Aufbau einer Stimulus-Datenbank für Anwendungen in der Virtuellen Akustik‘”, in: *Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 2017* (Kiel), 229-213.
- [8] Leckschat, D., Kreuer, O., Reinhard, R., Projektdokumentation Orgel-Aufnahme 2017 (Ursprungsfassung); Bearbeitung für Musterdokumentation: Epe, C., Hochschule Düsseldorf 2017

Appendix I

Model licensing agreement covering rights to audio production for use in acoustics

Appendix II

Checklist for documenting audio productions for scientific applications in acoustics

Appendix III

Sample documentation for an audio production

Disclaimer

The following Appendix 1, License Agreement, has been elaborated regarding german copyright law, and then has been translated into English.

However, copyright and media legislation is differing significantly in other countries. So please check for specific rules. DEGA is not responsible for any violations of laws when the licensing agreement ist used in other countries than Germany.

Licensing Agreement

between

Mr./Ms.-----

(Name, Address, Mailing address, DoB, Phone)

- hereinafter "Artist" -

and

German Acoustical Society. (DEGA)

Alte Jakobstraße 88

10179 Berlin

- hereinafter "Licensee"

Preamble

Licensee is a non-profit scientific association with the mission of promoting acoustics in that capacity. It brings together its members and all parties with an interest in acoustics and promotes knowledge exchanges between domestic and also foreign colleagues.

To this end, Licensee is currently undertaking a project whose aim is to develop new, three-dimensional audio formats for science and research that promote a better spatial reproduction and more intensive listening experience.

The project's underlying concept consists of making available a collection of acoustic stimuli organized in a data base in the public domain for scientific uses.

To aid in the evaluation of the new technologies will require high-quality audio recordings from the fields of music, speech, sounds and other test signals on which the artist in question will collaborate. The project consists of making the said audio recordings and documenting them in a comprehensive manner.

The parties to this agreement agree that Licensee is to be granted every known right of reproduction and possible use. This expressly applies both to exploiting the recordings in the Internet or other medium (film, television, CD-ROM, etc.) and to images and videos shot during the audio recording sessions (e.g., for a “the making of” documentary).

The overall project goal is to ultimately create a public domain library of audio formats supporting scientific and research developments for use by all.

§ 1 Object of the Agreement/ License

The object of the agreement is the corresponding contribution by the artist to an audio recording agreed on in advance of

- Instrumental passages
- spoken texts
- sung passages
- other sounds
-

The recordings will be made pursuant to the wishes or instructions of Licensee. The provisions agreed to herein also apply to (individual) compositional approaches by the artist to the acoustic performance.

Artist vouches for being entitled to an unlimited conveyance of rights. Artist conveys to Licensee the exclusive right to reproduce, process, disseminate or otherwise utilize the agreed-on audio recordings.

The Artist transfers to the Licensee the exclusive right to copy, process, distribute or otherwise use the respective audio recordings. The Artist also grants the Licensee, insofar as the Licensee is not already considered as the creator of the respective performances, the exclusive right unlimited as to time, place, and content to use each of the audio recordings in any way whatsoever. The Licensee is expressly granted the right to grant sublicenses and to transfer the rights granted to Licensee to third parties. In particular, the Licensee is expressly granted the right to put the work or parts thereof in the public domain, meaning that it can be made available to anyone for their own free use or at Licensee's discretion under other forms of use such as a Creative Commons license. Artist's approval will not be required in that case. The grant of rights also covers unknown forms of use.

§ 2 Payment

Licensee will pay Artist the one-time sum of _____EUR for the user rights granted under this Agreement. This amount will be due and payable within two weeks of the signing of the Agreement. Artist will not receive any further compensation for his/her contribution whether from the Licensee or from third parties.

Should Artist be subject to value added tax (VAT), the VAT due will be added to the one-time payment.

§ 3 Copyright holder designation

Artist agrees that Licensee is expressly under no obligation to designate Artist as the copyright holder in a suitable manner when reproducing or disseminating the work and to obligate any third party to do so. Instead, any naming of Artist is at the discretion of the Licensee.

§ 4 Processing

At no time will further processing require Artist's consent. In addition, modifications through, for example, sampling, loops, dynamic processing, etc. are permitted without qualification. Any claims by the Artist are satisfied by the payment agreed to hereunder.

§ 5 Final provisions

Modifications or additions to this Agreement and any side understandings regarding this Agreement must be made in writing to be effective. They are to be designated as such. Changes to this provision or the parties agreeing to waive written changes must nevertheless be in written form. Oral agreements outside this Agreement are void.

This Agreement is governed exclusively by the laws of the Federal Republic of Germany. The place of performance and fulfillment is Berlin. To the extent permissible, the competent jurisdiction for any disputes whatsoever arising from or in connection with this Agreement, including any obligations deriving from executing this Agreement or in connection therewith, is Berlin.

If any provisions of this Agreement shall be held to be invalid or unenforceable for any reason, or should this Agreement be found to have a gap, the remaining provisions shall continue to be valid and enforceable. To replace ineffective or unworkable provisions or to fill a gap a legally permissible appropriate provision shall apply that comes closest to what the parties to this Agreement intended or would have intended.

Date, Place

Date, Place

(Artist)

(Licensee)

7 Appendix II

Checklist for documenting audio productions for scientific applications in acoustics

Data base attributes:

Solo/Ensemble

Instrument

Year recorded:

Room volume

Room height

Room length

Room width

Reverberation time

Impulse response present? (yes/no)

Quiescent level

Calibrated? (y/n)

Microphones used

Sampling rate

Bitrate

Type of material:

- Melody (y/n)
- Single tone (y/n)
- Musical scale (y/n)
- Chords (y/n)
- Composition (y/n)

Note material (score) available (y/n)

Images (y/n)

Video (y/n)

Sample mix (y/n)

Preview Material (Yes/No/photos/video/sound)

Other/Comments

Sample

*Project documentation for
“Production of audio material for the DEGA Sound Data Base”*

“Organ recording”

Max Sampleman
Sample Production Studio, Samplehausen
mail@adresse.de , Tel.: +49-(0)123- 456789

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1. Recording environment

1.1. Room geometry

The church interior with its vaults and apses is a complex structure. At recording time, a church floor plan with measurements was not available, making it necessary to take them independently. To capture the dimensions, a random sample of spaces was measured and extrapolated to the total interior. To calculate volume, a rectangular solid-shaped interior was assumed using appropriate averaging.

The resulting measurements and volumes are shown in Table 1.1.

Width	17.37 m
Length	37.60 m
Height	10.25 m
Volume	6,691.581 m ³

Tabelle 1.1 Room measurements and volumes

Figure 1.1 shows the church structure with a gallery situated about 4 meters above the floor. On the gallery sits the organ whose pipes and case reach to the church ceiling. On the gallery's forward edge (facing the room) is a positive organ and the organ console (see the cover page image).

The surface materials inside the church, as expected, vary greatly. The walls, columns and floor (incl. the gallery) are mostly made of marble or other hard stone. In the church itself are located 72 wooden benches and a total of 21 windows. To form a better picture of the various materials and how they are distributed, the appendix contains images of the church, including a 3D model of the room.

Figure 1.1 Church floor plan with room dimension

1.2. Microphone positioning

Figure 1.2 – Positions of the microphones

Figure 1.2 shows the microphone positioning inside the church. A total of nine microphones were used in recording the organ. Two AKG C414 were set up about 5 meters from the great organ up on the gallery. These were for directly recording the great organ in stereo panorama, hence they were placed about 38 centimeters (cm) apart and at a 40° angle to each other at a height of 2.14 meters above the gallery with cardioid characteristics. Each of these microphones was paired with an omnidirectional measurement microphone (Behringer ECM8000) placed above the recording mic capsules at heights of about 1 cm. They could thus be used later after calibration as a sound level reference for the AKG C414.

Figure 1.3 – Microphoning of the great organ with two AKG C414s and calibrated reference measurement mics

Since the pipes of the great organ in part placed apart and the positive organ is located behind the console, the latter organ was separately microphoned. Because, compared to the great organ, it is not particularly wide at 2.6 meters, it was only recorded in mono with a Sennheiser MKH800 set to cardioid. It sat atop a 4.5-meter tall stand placed about 2.5 meters from the positive organ and was aimed directly at its center. For a later level reference, here also a calibrated Behringer ECM800 measurement mic was set up with the help of a gooseneck about 1 cm above the MKH8000's capsule (Figure 1.4 right).

For picking up a reverberation plume, the middle of the church room was fitted with two Sennheiser MKH800s as room microphones. These were set to omnidirectional at a height of 4.9 meters and 22 cm apart and roughly 8.7 meters from the positive organ microphone. Mounted on a stereo track they were used as stereo room microphones. Because of the relatively small gap between the two MKH800s, only one measurement mic was positioned midway between them. The measurement mic's capsule here was at the same height of those of the room microphones (see Fig. 1.4, left side).

Figure 1.4 – Room microphones in church middle (left); the positive organ's mic is shown at right.

1.3. Room acoustics

After the room dimensions were approximated ([Section 1.1](#)), the reverberation time and quiescent level were measured. Used for several readings lasting 30 seconds each was an NTI XL2 measuring instrument placed in mid-church on a cushioned bench. Due to the building’s low sound damping, recordings and quiescent level measurements were done at night (minimal street traffic).

The average readings from the quiescent level measurements are shown in Table 1.2.

L _{Aeq_dt} [dB]	L _{Aeq} [dB]	L _{AF-max_dt} [dB]	L _{AFT5eq} [dB]	L _{Zeq_dt} [dB]	L _{Zeq} [dB]	L _{Ceq_dt} [dB]	L _{Ceq} [dB]	L _{AF95%} [dB]
27.62	27.79	28.09	30.19	44.89	45.69	41.31	41.41	26.91

Table 1.2 - Quiescent level in mid-church

In addition to the quiescent level, the reverberation time was measured in octave bands. This was done by placing in the middle of the church, roughly near where the room mics were positioned, a loudspeaker of the Genelec 1031A type at about 1 meter above the floor (Figure 1.6 left) and pointing it at the altar that faces the organ. Approximately 7 meters behind the speaker, we positioned the NTI XL2 measurement instrument on a foam-padded chair (Figure 1.6 right). The excitation signal was supplied by an NTI MR2 Minirator.

Figure 1.6 – Set up for measuring reverb time: loudspeaker aimed at altar (left), measurement instrument ca. 7 meter behind loud speaker (right)

The measurements were taken with the help of 7-second pink noise signal bursts supplied by the MR2 and reproduced through the loudspeaker. The measurement equipment meanwhile recorded the reverberation time in several passes as octave bands which yielded the average values in Table 1.3.

For measuring a room impulse response, a shot from a starter pistol was fired from the gallery and recorded by all microphones.

Band[Hz]	63	125	250	500	1000	2000	4000	8000
T ₆₀ [s]	3.90	4.62	4.08	3.79	3.57	3.03	2.14	1.11
Hall radius [m]	2.36	2.17	2.31	2.40	2.47	2.68	3.19	4.43

Table 1.3 – Reverberation level of the church in octave bands

To determine the hall radius for the relevant octave band, we used the average volume approximately determined in [Section 1.1](#) and the measured reverberation time.

1.4. Recording systems

All recording systems (transmission equipment, microphones, accessories) were listed in an Excel spreadsheet and can be found together with the related data sheets in the recording system index.

Settings:

DAW (Cubase 8.5 Pro) and interface were used with the following settings:

- Sampling rate: 48 kHz
- Bitrate: 24 Bit

Absolute sound pressure level (SPL):

For the purpose of documenting the absolute SPL during recording, each measurement microphone (reference) was registered with a **94 dB SPL** calibration tone. With this calibration tone, it was possible to make a level compensation between reference and recording mics in a digital audio workstation (DAW software) by using the Waves Plus Loudness Meter (WLM). With a generally adjusted level it was possible to edit the calibration tone before each recording microphone track and export them together. The resulting recording can be leveled and reproduced via this calibration tone in a subsequent playback system.

2. Audio contents

2.1. The instrument

The church organ used for the recordings was built in 1982 by the Berlin-based organ maker Karl Schuke of the Berliner Orgelwerkstatt GmbH. The instrument is located in the **St. Jacobus Church in Hilden**. Assisting us in operating it was the church organist and our contact person Carlos Reigadas. The disposition (combining the registers (stops), assisting with playing) was done by **Friedhelm Hohman und Josef Zimmermann**. The construction is modeled on a Romantic organ. The organ-playing action is pneumatic, the stop action electric. Table 2.1 shows the organ pipe names and their stops.

Figure 2.1 – The organ stop console

For the recordings, registers were used individually and in a large variety of combinations.

I Great organ C – a ³			Positive organ C – a ³			III Swell organ C – a ³			Pedal organ C - f1		
Nr.	Name	Stop	Nr.	Name	Stop	Nr.	Name	Stop	Nr.	Name	Stop
1	Nachthorn	16'	16	Principal	8'	28	Bourdon	16'	44	Prinzipal	16'
2	Principal	8'	17	Gedackt	8'	29	Rohrflöte	8'	45	Subbass	16'
3	Holzflöte	8'	18	Quintade	8'	30	Geigenprinzipal	8'	46	Bordun	16'
4	Gemshorn	8'	19	Praestant	4'	31	Salizonal	8'	47	Quinte	10 ² / ₃ '
5	Gamba	8'	20	Spitzflöte	4'	32	Vox Coelestis	8'	48	Oktave	8'
6	Octave	4'	21	Schwegel	2'	33	Prinzipal	4'	49	Bassflöte	8'
7	Blockflöte	4'	22	Sesquialtera II		34	Traversflöte	4'	50	Choralbass	4'
8	Quinte	2 ² / ₃ '	23	Quinte	1 ¹ / ₃ '	35	Nasard	2 ² / ₃ '	51	Pommer	4'
9	Oktave	2'	24	Scharff IV		36	Bachflöte	2'	52	Hintersatz IV	
10	Kornett(IV-V)		25	Dulcian	16'	37	Terz	1 ³ / ₅ '	53	Posaune	16'
11	Mixtur V		26	Krummhorn	8'	38	Piccolo	1'	54	Trompete	8'
12	Zimbel III		27	Vox Humana	8'	39	Mixtur VI		55	Trompete	4'
13	Trompete	16'		<i>Tremulant</i>		40	Basson	16'			
14	Trompete	8'				41	Trompete	8'			
15	Trompete	4'				42	Oboe	8'			
						43	Clarino	4'			
							<i>Tremulant</i>				

Table 2.1 – Overview of the organs and their registers

The detuning of individual stops or pipes was determined by measurement at between 20 and 40 Cent above the 440 Hz tuning.

2.2. Musical content

Producing a recording of representative sounds made by a church organ differs fundamentally from recording “customary” instruments. This is because its many pipes and their stops (see Table 2.1) differ completely from one another both spatially and acoustically. In fact, they are much more comparable to a musical ensemble than a single instrument. This creates special challenges that had to be taken into consideration in deciding on and producing suitable musical content.

2.2.1. Distinguishing individual pipes

To facilitate documenting the acoustical crosstalk (similar to having musicians in an ensemble distributed over a room), DEGA guidelines require recording each instrument (in the organ’s case the stops) individually at its position at all microphones. The spatial separation that also occurs with organs was allowed for by individually recording the organ pipes for each audio example and each registration. To get the full impact, using the same process this was followed by coupling individual manuals (keyboards) to once more record all pipes in unison (except for the pedal organ which cannot be linked).

2.2.2. Registrations

Since the pipe registrations differ in sound individually and in combination, however, to compare the pipes requires seeking a roughly uniform sound. For this purpose we used the basic registers possessed by each pipe: Prinzipal (flue pipes) and Trompete (flue pipes) as well as a full registration (Tutti). These allow a maximum broadband comparison of the characteristic organ sounds. The only exception involved the swell organ/positive organ. Here, support was provided with other flue pipe registers and the positive organ, in which other lingual pipe registers substituted for the absent Trompete register. All registers were played at the same sound level (8”).

A precise overview of all registrations can be found in the index under tracks → single tracks.

2.2.3. Composition

The most fundamental aspect in making as broadband a comparison as possible of characteristic organ sounds is the choice of a suitable musical content. A neutral basis is achieved by using basic musical building blocks such as scales and harmonies. For a practical reference to organ music, chords broken arpeggio-style and an excerpt from a popular organ piece were also recorded. Figures 2.2 through 2.5 illustrate musical notations for the rendered audio materials.

Tonleiter

C-Dur

$\text{♩} = 100$

Figure 2.2 Musical scale

Akkorde

C-Dur

$\text{♩} = 100$

Figure 2.3 Chords in C major

Arpeggio

a - F - G - E

Music by Riccardo Reinhard

$\text{♩} = 100$

Figure 2.4 Arpeggio

Toccata und Fuge in d-Moll

Fuge: Takt 1 - 10

Music by Johann Sebastian Bach

Figure 2.5 Toccata and fugue in D minor

Copyrights:

Musical scale, chords, and arpeggio are in the public domain because of the inadequate threshold of originality. Under §64 of the Copyright Law, the Toccata and Fugue in D minor is in the public domain, since its composer (Johann Sebastian Bach) has been deceased for more than 70 years.

Musician:

All recordings were played by **Riccardo Reinhard**.

2.2.4. Audio data

Total number of audio files: 372

- Mix Files: 61 (sorted by organ, register, and music content)
- Single tracks: 311 (sorted by organ, register, and music content)
- Audioformat: Wave format, word length 24 bit, sampling rate 48 kHz

	Scales	Chords	Arpeggios	Toccata
Length of recording [s]	26	26	19	38
Peak level [dBFS]	-12 to -3 (Not shown individually because of the mass of data)			

3. Appendices

3.1. Data storage device contents/Zip file etc.

Directory	Type
Tracks	Recorded single tracks incl. reference audio before starting (sorted by organ, register, and musical content)
Measurements	Tables of geometrical measurements, noise floor level and reverberation time, room impulse responses
Images	Photos of the room, also microphone positioning and various sketches
Videos	Videos of setting up, also the individual recording sessions
Recording systems	Lists of equipment used, with their related data sheets
Notes	Notes of the recorded audio examples
Cubase Project	Cubase 8.5 file for the recording project
3D-Model	3D-model of the church and pictures of the model

Table 3.1 – Contents of the data storage device/zip files

3.2. Pictures of the church

(Examples, more content on the data storage device/zip file, etc.)

3.3. 3D-model of the room

(Examples, more content on the data storage device/zip file, etc.)

3.4. Recording system

3.4.1. Inventory list

	Description	Manufacturer	Model	Count
Recording equipment	Interface	Focusrite	Liquid Saffire 56	1
	PreAmp	Behringer	ADA 8000	1
	Laptop	Apple	MacBook Pro (13", 2012)	1
	Headset	Beyerdynamic	DT 770 Pro (80 Ohm)	1
	Headset	Beyerdynamic	DT 770 Pro (250 Ohm)	1
Microphones	Direct (HW/SW/PW; RP)	AKG	C414	3
	Room	Sennheiser	MKH 800	2
	Measurement mic	Behringer	ECM 8000	4
	Measuring equipment	Lasermessgerät	Bosch	1
	Sound level meter	NTI Audio	XL2	1
	Noise generator	NTI Audio	Minirator MR-PRO	1
	Loudspeaker	Genelec	1031A	1
Accessories	Multicore	Thomann	the sssnake MC8	1
	XLR cable	Neutrik	20m	9
	Jack extension cable	Thomann	the sssnake SPP2050	1
	Large stands	unbekannt	ca. 5m	2
	Small stands	Millenium	MS-2005	4

3.4.2. Data sheets

(See contents on data storage device/zip, etc.)